

Role of Computer-Based Management Information System in Research and Development of Technical and Vocational Education

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Abstract

This paper discusses the role of management information system in the research and development of technical and vocational education. It is divided into seven sections. The first section is introduction where definitions of technical and vocational education are presented. The subsequent sections discuss development of technical and vocational education in Nigeria, research and development of technical and vocational education in technical and vocational education, management information system in technical and vocational education, role of computer-based management information system in the research and development of technical and vocational education, conclusion and recommendations.

Keywords: Management, information, system, research, development, technical, vocational and education.

Introduction

There is a general view in literature that technical and vocational education (TVE) is the education provided to equip students with skill, knowledge and attitude for work. For instance, Ogwo and Oranu (2006) define technical and vocational education as education offered to enable students acquire skill in order to be gainfully employed. It was also defined by Olaitan, Nwachukwu, Igbo, Onyemachi and Ekong (1999) as an education geared towards preparing individual for work. UNESCO-UNEVOC (2010) defines it as an education that leads to the acquisition of skill and knowledge needed in the world of work. UNESCO and ILO (2002) refers to TVE as a term used to describe those aspects of the educational process involving, in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences, and the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge related to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life, which is also adopted by Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013).

The above description indicates that TVE plays very important role in national development. TVE is intended to equip individual with the knowledge and skill needed to function in job roles in different sectors of the economy such as agriculture, education, commerce, technology among others. TVE is also intended to equip individual with skill and knowledge for self-reliance. This means that graduates of technical and vocational education can be self-employed. For instance, an individual who learnt electrical installation from a technical school or a training centre, can go ahead to open a small electrical firm with the function of providing such services to the public. This way he receives income for himself. He could also provide needed

services to the public and thereby contributes to national development. By acquiring skills for employment, individuals who gains such skills will reduce the number of unemployed in the country. Consequently, poverty level in the country is likely to reduce. This is in line with the view of Oviawe (2017) that TVE equips people with skills and knowledge for employment and livelihood. Further, TVE serves as a tool for technological growth. TVE produces individuals who apply scientific knowledge to provide solution to environmental problems and to better the life of humanity. Applying scientific knowledge to provide solution to problem of the society is regarded as technology (Olujide, 2000; Anaele & Okoro, 2014).

Considering the important role that technical and vocational education plays manpower development for the society, it is pertinent that adequate attention be given to its development. Research plays an important role in any process of development. Countries of the world that have made great strides in their economies hold research and development to high esteem. Similarly, organisations that want to maintain competitive edge maintain a high standard research and development department who constantly conduct research on products, market situation among others to ensure that quality of product continues to gain customer satisfaction. Technical and vocational education is a product and therefore research and development of TVE should also be given optimum attention.

Research and development therefore plays significant role in the development of TVE to achieve the goal of preparing recipients to acquire skills needed in the labour market. Ukuma and Ochedikwu (2013) opine that research and development (R&D) in technical and vocational education is a means of job creation and economic recovery in Nigeria. When jobs are created, more individuals who are jobless will be meaningfully engaged and they will have income to take care of their children. Their economic lives will improve and in turn poverty level will be reduced in the country. Ebhota (2014) stressed that advancement in science, engineering and technology, which guarantees innovation, depends of R&D. Research in different sectors of an economy will generate knowledge on ways of improvement. For example, in the agricultural sector, research could reveal better ways of preserving food to minimize wastage and thus ensure food security. Research and development in TVE should therefore be held to high esteem if any meaningful development in this sector is expected.

One of the challenges facing TVE especially in Nigeria is inadequate data and information for ascertaining progress in TVE and lack of reliable and adequate labour market information (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2005; Idris, Hassan, Osaigbovo, Christopher & Ngwu, 2014; Okolocha, 2012). Such information could be information about the employment destinations of graduates of TVE. It could also be information about the requirement in the labour market in terms of current demand for skills and the type of skill and how many skill men are needed in particular occupation. Such information could guide curriculum planners in making necessary adjustment in curriculum for TVE delivery. Such information could also help policy makers in TVE in enacting policies for effective management and administration of TVE. FRN (2005) lamented that this ill situation of lack of labour market information leads to increase in unemployment. The authors of this article believe that management information system in TVE could contribute to research and development of technical and vocational education in Nigeria. It was based on this that the present article is written to discuss the role of management information system in the research and development of TVE. Moreover, Onyeike and Owuama (2012) recommended the establishment of national data bank to obtain ready data and statistics for planning and implementing higher education programme in Nigeria.

Development of Technical and Vocational Education in Nigeria

The Federal Government of Nigeria, recognizing the important role that TVE plays in national development, moved to establish pre vocational schools in the mid-1900s, in the form of handcraft and trade centers with the purpose of producing craftsmen and technicians, in wood and metal working and other craft/arts activities. Further development of TVE resulted in the establishment of technical colleges, polytechnics, monotronics and colleges of technology in Nigeria (FRN, 2013; Okelola, 1972). Furthermore, government has initiated other programmes to boost TVE in Nigeria such as National Directorate of employment (NDE); Industrial Training Fund (ITF); National Poverty Alleviation Programmes (NAPEP); skill acquisition programmes by the Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC). The aim of all these schools and programmes is to enhance the acquisition of practical skill for gainful employment by citizens (Adewale, Siyanbola, & Siyanbola, 2014; Audu, Yusri & Farhad, 2013; FRN, 2013; Gumbari, 2009; Idris, Hassan, Osaigbovo, Christopher, & Ngwu, 2014; Jahun, 2017; National Board for Technical Education, NBTE, 2011; Ogbuanya, & Okoli, 2014).

The efforts by successive government of Nigeria and the private sector in the development of technical and vocational education, have yielded some success stories, particularly, in terms of graduating students from TVE institutions and also access to TVE. At least one of the positive results is that institutions offering technical and vocational education are producing graduates for Nigerian as a country (Akinyemi, Ofem & Ikuenomore, 2012; Arikpo, 2014). But success story in terms of inventions born out of research and development is limited. Little is known about what TVE institutions have produced to enhance development in agriculture, commerce and industry in Nigeria. A literature search by the authors of this article found a report by Olatunji (2018), the rector of Federal Polytechnic, that the tricycle widely known as “Keke” in Nigeria was invented earlier in School of Technology, Kwara State but for absence of commercialisation, someone else took the invention to China. Today, it is used in many states of Nigeria. According to Olatunji students designed the solar power used in almost all departments in Federal Polytechnic Offa. Olatunji added that students also designed the e-voting software product used for their union election. Olatunji further added that other products are being invented in technical institutions in Nigeria (para. 1-8). Further report by Opatayibo (2017) reveals that a drone has been locally constructed in Nigeria to among other things, aid security personnel in surveillance and management of traffic (para. 1-7).

In view of the above highlighted roles of technical and vocational education and the success stories evident in the reports presented, it is obvious that research and development in technical and vocational education in Nigeria will go a long way to curb the problems and challenges facing TVE and thereby enhance development in Nigeria. The national policy on education by Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013), stipulates that research and development serves as a major tool that can be used to achieve the goals of tertiary education. It therefore implies that through research in technical and vocational education, new products and services could be developed. Such product and services could be used to enhance activities in a particular sector of the economy and thereby enhance development in the country. Research into ways of creating product and services for enhancing development is associated with the concept of research and development (R&D).

Research and Development (R&D) in Technical and Vocational Education

The Nigerian Content Development and Monitoring Board (2016) defines research and development as any activity such as a study, an investigation or analysis conducted to solve a

problem, add to a body of knowledge, leads to process improvement or result in a new technology development. Research and development (R&D) according to Gay, Mills and Airasian (2012) is the application of research methods to ascertain the needs of customers and after which, develop a product or service to meet such needs. Gay, Mill and Airasian added that R&D in education seeks not to test or formulate a theory but focuses on developing a product to serve educational purposes. Hall (2006) describes R&D as the entire activities carried out by a firm, from the stage of scientific research to design and development to testing and commercialization of a product meant to fulfill specific needs. A product here could be a solid object such as an instructional resource developed to aid instruction. It could also be an educational service designed to meet a need in education. Furthermore, it could be a solid object developed to meet an industrial or business purpose.

Research and development according to Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD, 2015) consists of three major activities which are basic research, applied research and experimental development. Basic research is research work undertaken to gain knowledge of a phenomenon through development or refinement of a theory without any intention for immediate application of its results; applied research is the research conducted to test the applicability of a theory in solving practical problem. Experimental development is research conducted based practical experience and knowledge from research to develop or improve new or existing products or processes (Gay, Mill and Airasian, 2012; OECD, 2015). Typical example of basic research is the research study by Ivan Pavlov which result in the behaviorist theory called classical conditioning. Knowledge from this study has given rise to ideas about reinforcement in learning. A research study conducted to test if reinforcement will enhance learning for particular set of students is an example of applied research. An example of experimental development is using knowledge of multimedia principles by Clark and Mayer (2011) in developing instructional materials for effective teaching and learning.

By the above description, it implies that R&D in technical and vocational education is the process of conducting research to aid gaining knowledge and understanding of the concept of TVE and using such knowledge and experiences from practice to develop products and services to further improve TVE. It will involve the process of applying research methods to deduce the needs of TVE and developing products to meet such needs. One typical example of research and development in TVE is that illustrated by Nwineh (2013) who observed that in carrying out practical exercises in electrical installation, materials for such practical may not always be readily available in the workshop when needed. Also, in some situations, it may not be very safe for students to conduct some practical. With this observation, he embarked on a research study to develop a simulated instructional package to enhance teaching and learning of domestic electrical installation. In this case, a product (simulated instructional package) is developed through research study to meet instructional need (absent of instructional resources).

Management Information System

The term Management Information System (MIS) is a combination of three words: management, information and system. Management is the act of organizing and coordinating resources to achieve an organization's goals. Information is a processed data while system is a group of interrelated components working together to achieve a common purpose by processing accepted input to produce an output (Al-Najjar in Al-Mamary, Shamsuddin and Aziati, 2014; Hardcastle, 2008; O'Brien & Marakas, 2011). Management information system (MIS) could then be described as a group of interrelated human and material resources that

work together in an organisation to coordinate the collection and processing of data to produce information needed to aid decision making for the purpose of achieving the goals of such an organization. In line with this, Bendoly (2008) describe MIS as an integrated system comprising the working together of human and machine to provide information to aid decision making process in an organization. Management information system is referred to as information system by Laudon and Laudon (2012) and defined as collection of interrelated components involved in collecting processing, storing, and distributing information for enhancing coordination, control, problem analysis; decision making and creation of new products in an organization. These interrelated components according to O'Brien and Marakas include human, software, hardware, communications networks, data resources, policies and procedures that work together in the achievement of the goals of the organization.

Management Information System in Technical and Vocational Education

Management information system in education refers to a system design to collect, integrate, process, maintain and disseminate data and information to aid planning, monitoring, analysis, evaluation for decision making in educational system (Nganjiozor, 2016). Consequently, management information system in TVE can refer to a system of interrelated components consisting of human, machines and software, designed for collecting data and information as input, processing such input data to aid in the development of technical and vocational education through analysis, evaluation and decision making on processed data. In technical and vocational education, inputs include provided fund; technical teachers and instructors; instructional resources such as machines, tools, materials; facilities such as electricity, water, building; workshops, production units, information and communication technology facilities; learning environment among others. The process include the instructional methods and strategies; programmes of activities employed to implement curriculum. The output include the competences students have developed as a result of going through the programme of study; the employment destinations of graduates from the TVE programme; impact on the society. Building a computer-based management system around these sources of data and information could be very instrumental to the research and development of technical and vocational education. The next section presents role that a computer-based information system plays in the research and development of TVE.

Role of Computer-Based MIS in the Research and Development of TVE

A computer-based management information system is a management information system that uses computer hardware software and other information and communication technologies such as internet, networks and humans to aid collection of data, storing of data, and retrieval of data to support decision making by management of an organization (Laudon & Laudon, 2012). Computer-based management information system could play very important role in research and development of TVE. These could be, among others, in the areas of data bank for TVE; information dissemination in TVE; effective monitoring and supervision in TVE; evaluation of TVE; curriculum development in TVE and decision making in TVE. These are discussed below.

MIS as Data Bank for Research and Development in TVE

Data is very important in any research exercise. Every research endeavour, requires the collection of data. Based on the collected data analysis could be conducted to reveal useful information that could be useful to consumers of such research. Any meaningful research for development in TVE depends on reliable data needed to be analyzed to produce useful information that can be used for development in TVE. For example, a research conducted to

survey skills need in the labour market could provide information needed by curriculum planners in TVE institutions to make adjustment in programme delivery.

MIS as Support for Information Dissemination in TVE

Information dissemination has to do with transmitting information to stakeholders in a system. In technical and vocational education, there are some information that needs to be disseminated to aid research and development. For example, information about employment destination of graduates of institutions in TVE is needed to ascertain what graduates of TVE are doing in their employment destinations.

Another set of information that needs dissemination is current practice in the industry for particular occupations, trades and businesses and the skills required to function in such areas. Furthermore, information about enrolment in TVE institutions could be used by government for planning towards funding, facility provision among others. These information could inform the teachers in TVE institutions on strategies needed to be employed in the instructional process to enhance the acquisition of such skill. Administrators and other stake holders in TVE could also be informed of facilities needed to be provided to aid instruction accordingly.

MIS as Support for Monitoring and supervision in TVE

Management information system enables utilization of information to monitor an educational system (Wako, 2003). With a computer-based management information system in TVE, monitoring of activities and progress can be made effectively and efficiently. Information needed for planning and strategizing for development, such as progress report of how well graduates of TVE are doing can easily be checked. Such information could also be useful in conducting action oriented research towards enhancing practice and development in TVE. Furthermore, such information also enhances supervision process in TVE as supervisors could use information to proactively take necessary action in their responsibilities.

MIS as Support for Evaluation in TVE

Programme evaluation is a very importance activity in the development of a programme. It is a systematic method employed to collect and analyse data about a programme, and use result of such analysis to proffer solution to questions that border on the success of the programme (Metz, 2007). When a programme is evaluated, judgment can be made and action can be taken to make adjustment or refine activities. All actions taken are to ensure development in the programme so evaluated. In the same vein, evaluation of TVE programme is very important to its development. In the process of evaluation, certain areas of weakness could be identified and appropriate solution could be proffered to enhance development in TVE. For example, if it is discovered from an evaluation exercise that graduates of TVE are not doing well in their places of employment, relevant authorities could use such information to swing into action in a bid to solve the problem of inefficiencies.

MIS and Curriculum Development in TVE

One of the very crucial activities during the process of designing and developing a curriculum is need analysis. During this activity, data is gathered about the need of the learner as well as immediate environment for which the learner in which he will function after leaving school. Such data as what skill needs exist in the labour market could inform the curriculum designer is setting goals and objectives of the curriculum intended for an educational programme (UNESCO, 1982). It therefore means that lack of or limited data can hamper on the process of

curriculum development for TVE that prepares students for the labour market. It can limit the content of the curriculum so produced.

MIS and Decision Making in TVE

It has been reiterated in this article that MIS enhances decision making. This is due to data and information needed for decision making that is readily available in MIS. Employing MIS in TVE could aid in the process of decision making as data needed in this wise will readily be available for government officials; school authorities; lecturers; private sector involved in technical and vocational education and training (TVET) and even students and trainees themselves. Having knowledge of skills needs in the labour market could guide intending students of TVET on how to make their choices. It could also help the career guidance counselor to administer career advice to students and trainees. Armed with such information, the students can take adequate decision as to the course to study. Being informed of skill needs in the labour market, government could be guided in taking decision as to expand a particular programme of study in TVE institutions or to limit intake for a particular programme for a period of time or to even limit programme of study to particular TVE institutions in a locality. For example, if it is found from data and information from a management information system agro activity is predominant in a locality, decision to establish related agricultural vocational programme will be justified.

Conclusion

From discussion in this paper, it is evident that technical and vocational education plays significant role in the development of any nation particularly in the area of skill development of individuals for employment. In light of the important role that TVE plays in national development, successive government and the private sector seek for ways of improving the development and access to TVE through establishment of TVE institutions skill development centres and programme. The effort to improve development and access to TVE especially in Nigeria has yielded some success stories especially in terms of producing graduates with good qualification. However, success stories in terms of research and development is limited. To enhance development in TVE in Nigeria, research and development (R&D) is crucial. But contingent to R&D in TVE is reliable data on labour market which could aid TVE institutions and other stakeholders in planning adequately for TVE.

Recommendations

Based on the discussion in this paper, the following recommendations are proffered;

1. Every institution offering technical and vocational education should design and develop a computer-based management information system. Such management information system should capture information about labour market skill demand, research achievements in the various fields of TVE,
2. Labour market research should be conducted frequently, by institutions offering technical and vocational education courses or programmes like polytechnics, colleges of education, colleges of technology, monotechnics, universities and others, at regular intervals: say ten (10) years interval.
3. Data and information so gathered should be stored in the database of the institution's management information system. The institutions involved should source for funding of this particular stream of research through government interventions and non-governmental organizations.

4. Institutions offering TVE programmes should conduct Comparative research studies: comparing especially, TVE systems of countries with similar economies. This could provide data and information about success stories.
4. A synergy should be initiated by TVE institutions to establish link with the industrial sector through a public relation activities to support two way information flow. Such synergy would help TVE institutions to have easy access to updated data.
5. The industrial and labour sectors should as part of its social responsibilities, publish bulletins and newsletters for minimum skill level required for a potential employment to a certain job role.

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